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Annotation

The article focuses on stylistic devices that are actively used in the literary text to show stylistic approaches in which the author's word choice, sentence structure, figurative language, and sentence arrangement all work together to establish mood, images, and meaning in the text. It also presents the importance of stylistic devices in the depiction of literary text

Keywords: Stylistics, stylistic devices, word literary, text figure of speech

Аннотация

В статье основное внимание уделяется стилистическим приемам, которые активно используются в художественном тексте, чтобы показать стилистические приемы, в которых авторский выбор слов, структура предложения, образный язык и расположение предложений вместе создают настроение, образы и смысл в тексте. Также показано значение стилистических приемов в изображении художественного текста.

Ключевые слова: Стилистические стилистические приемы слова литературный текст фигура речи.

Stylistic devices occur often in all kinds of literature. For instance, in Shakespeare's play *The Comedy of Errors*, Antipholus states that "I to the world am like a drop of water, / That in the ocean seeks another drop." This is a simile because Antipholus claims to be similar to a drop of water in order to represent his internal state. Another example of a stylistic device is the line, "All the world's a stage," from Jaques in Shakespeare's play *As You Like It*. This is a metaphor because the line doesn't literally mean that the world is a stage, but rather is a way of noting similarities between life and theatre.

There are a lot of different types of stylistic devices. Frequently used devices include metaphor, when a writer acts as if two clearly different things are the same so that they can be compared, or simile, when a writer states that two quite different things are alike for the sake of comparison. Other stylistic devices include personification, hyperbole, oxymoron, allusion, alliteration, and anaphora.

Metaphor as a Stylistic Device

A metaphor is a type of stylistic device where the writer links disparate ideas that do not fit together literally but can be interpreted figuratively as a comparison. An example of a metaphor would be the statement, "This library is an ocean of knowledge." The library is obviously not an ocean, so a literal interpretation of the sentence would make little sense. However, interpreted figuratively, it is clear that the library is compared to an ocean in order to express that it feels vast and deep. The metaphor reveals an aspect of the library that may not come across as vividly if the writer simply said that the library was large. Another example of a metaphor would be if a writer stated, "The reader devoured the book." The person in question is not literally eating a book, but the metaphor of eating is used to portray the speed with which the person reads and takes in information it.

Simile as a Rhetorical Device

A simile is a rhetorical device in which the writer asserts a similarity between things that do not actually have much in common in order to emphasize one particular feature that they do share. A simile can generally be distinguished from a metaphor by the presence of the word "like" or "as." For instance, the statement "The class was like a steep mountain" is a simile because the writer compares the class and a mountain to express that taking the class had certain features of climbing a mountain, such as being lengthy and difficult. Another example of a simile would be the statement, "The tree stood as tall as a skyscraper." In this simile, the tree is compared to a skyscraper in height in order to emphasize the way it towers over the viewer.

Personification as a Figure of Speech

Personification occurs when a writer describes something as if it had the characteristics or agency of a person, even though it does not. An example of personification would be the sentence, "The stream whispered along the ground." The word "whispered" implies that the stream can talk as if it were a person. The personification allows the writer to make the sound of the stream more vivid in the mind of the reader. Another example of personification would be the sentence, "The door groaned as it was opened." Groaning is something that a person does to express irritation, but here the writer suggests that the door, which has not been opened in a long time, makes a sound like groaning as if it were irritated to be opened. In this way, the personification helps bring the scene to life.

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To sum up, understanding style is an important aspect of modeling inherent subjectivity in text. We presented some basic stylistic devices with examples to understand and qualify stylistic aspects of text at lexical, syntactic, and semantic-level. Using stylistic devices everyone can present their own cultural concepts, notions, identities, ideas and view points in the communicative speech and literary text in the appropriate way through the usage of cultural elements.

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